

HOMOGENIZATION OF SANDWICH PANELS WITH COMPLEX MICROSTRUCTURE

Bharani Ravishankar^{1*}, Anurag Sharma¹, B. V. Sankar², R.T. Haftka³

¹Graduate Student, ²Ebaugh Professor, ³Distinguished Professor
Mechanical & Aerospace Engineering, University of Florida, Gainesville, FL 32611, U.S.A.

* Corresponding author (b2harani@ufl.edu)

Keywords: sandwich structures, homogenization, micro-mechanics, unit-cell, periodic boundary conditions, transverse shear stiffness,

1. General Introduction

Recent developments in materials and manufacturing have changed the ways in which sandwich panels are fabricated. Advances in core materials, ceramic and other types of composites, foams and joining techniques have given rise to novel designs of sandwich cores and panels. Sandwich structures are envisioned for cooling channels for combustors, engines and compressors; heat shields for hypersonic vehicles, containment shroud for fan blades in rotating machinery, etc. Sandwich structures are also candidates for many marine structures such as ship structures and submarines. Recently sandwich panels (Fig. 1 and 2) have been considered for integrated thermal protection systems which combine the insulation function of traditional heat shields and load carrying function of vehicle's outer structure.

Fig.1. Schematic of a corrugated sandwich panel

Traditionally sandwich panels are analyzed using shear deformable plate theory, which requires the in plane stiffness matrices A , B and D , and transverse shear stiffness coefficients A_{44} and A_{55} . Calculation of the above stiffness coefficients is straight forward for simple core configurations. However, the core microstructure can become complicated due to the

manufacturing technique used or optimal design considerations. In that case special homogenization methods are required to estimate the stiffness properties of the sandwich panel.

In this paper we develop a finite element based homogenization procedure for predicting the equivalent stiffness properties of sandwich structures. Periodicity of the structure in the plane of the panel facilitates micromechanical analysis to obtain the equivalent stiffness properties, the extensional stiffness matrix $[A]$, coupling stiffness matrix $[B]$, and bending stiffness $[D]$. Deformations are applied to the representative volume element (RVE) of the structure, and the resulting forces are used to calculate the equivalent stiffness properties.

Fig. 2. Schematic view of ITPS sandwich structure with foam

The design configuration with face sheets and corrugated core produces pronounced shear deformation in the sandwich panel. To effectively homogenize the 3D structure into an equivalent 2D orthotropic plate, transverse shear stiffness (A_{44} and A_{55}) should be determined. We have developed a method which combines finite element analysis and analytical methods to obtain the transverse shear

stiffness. With all the stiffness properties determined, the accuracy of the homogenization procedure is evaluated by comparing the response of the 2D orthotropic plate with a 3D analysis of the sandwich panel.

2 Homogenization Procedures

2.1 Equivalent Stiffness Properties: The unit cell is basically the primary block of the structure that repeats itself. The unit cell is subjected to six linearly independent deformation field to determine the equivalent extension and bending stiffness properties of the panel (A , B , D matrices). The deformations are applied as periodic displacement boundary conditions (PBC) which includes three mid-plane strains $(\varepsilon_x, \varepsilon_y, \gamma_{xy})$ and three curvatures $(\kappa_x, \kappa_y, \kappa_{xy})$. These deformations create in-plane forces (N_x, N_y, N_{xy}) and moments (M_x, M_y, M_{xy}) in the unit cell. The constitutive relation between the in-plane forces and moments and the mid-plane strains and curvature yields the in-plane stiffness properties of the structure. The unit cell is modeled in ABAQUS, a commercial finite element software.

2.2 Transverse shear stiffness: To obtain the transverse shear stiffness, the panel a one-dimensional cantilevered plate with unit cells in the longitudinal direction (x -direction) is analyzed. Displacement boundary conditions are applied such that at $x=0$, $u=w=0$; and at $x=L$, $u=0$ and $w(L)=\text{constant}$. Using the finite element analysis the tip forces required for the aforementioned displacements are calculated. Beam deflection in general is due to bending and shear. The bending deflection is calculated analytically using the A , B and D matrices. The shear deformation is estimated as the difference between the total deflection obtained from the FE analysis and the bending deflection obtained from the analytical method. From the shear deflection the transverse shear stiffness is estimated. The tip deflection is given by

$$w(L) = \frac{FL^3}{3D_{11}} - \frac{ML^2}{2D_{11}} + \frac{FL}{A_{55}} \quad (1)$$

where F and M , respectively, are the transverse force and couple at $x=L$.

3 Accuracy of Homogenization procedure

In order to assess the accuracy of homogenization procedure a sandwich panel is analyzed using both finite elements and the analytical method. The analytical method uses the homogenized properties and uses the shear deformable plate theory (SDPT). The panel is subjected to a uniform pressure load P under clamped boundary conditions at $x=0$.

Fig 3. 1D sandwich panel subjected to pressure load under clamped boundary conditions at $x=0$.

The deflection along the bottom face sheet of the finite element model is compared with the analytical model using equation (2).

$$w(x) = \frac{2P}{A_{55}} \left(Lx - \frac{x^2}{2} \right) + \frac{2P}{2D_{11}} \left(\frac{L^2 x^2}{2} + \frac{x^4}{12} - \frac{Lx^3}{3} \right) \quad (2)$$

The plate is also analyzed using classical lamination theory, CLPT (infinite shear stiffness) to show the importance of transverse shear stiffness.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Homogenized Properties: Initially the $[ABD]$ matrix was predicted through homogenization method for an isotropic panel. It was compared with the $[ABD]$ matrix obtained analytically using the Classical Lamination Theory. Both the analytical and FE values agreed well with less than 1% difference. Then the actual composite material properties were considered and the $[ABD]$ matrix was determined.

4.2 Transverse shear stiffness: The transverse shear stiffness A_{44} and A_{55} are cross sectional properties and hence are supposed to be a constant for a given microstructure.

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Fig 4. Transverse shear stiffness A_{55} as a function of length of the 1-D plate

Figure 4 shows the variation of the transverse shear stiffness as a function of number of unit cells (length of the panel). It can be seen that though the transverse shear stiffness is high for fewer unit cells, it converges as the number of unit cell increases.

Table 1. Transverse shear stiffness variation for ‘ n ’ unit cells panel

n	$A_{55} N/m$
4	6.64×10^5
8	6.17×10^5
16	5.98×10^5

The convergence of the transverse shear stiffness could be assessed using the above table and the following equation (3).

$$\frac{k_3 - k_2}{k_3 - k_1} = \left(\frac{N_1}{N_2} \right)^\alpha \quad (3)$$

Where k_1, k_2, k_3 are the values of A_{55} for $n = 4, 8, 16$ respectively. N_1/N_2 is the ratio of the unit cells (here $N_1/N_2 = 0.5$). α is the convergence factor which should be greater than one for convergence. From Table 1, the value of $\alpha = 1.69$ which promises converge of the stiffness value.

The transverse shear stiffness can be predicted for large number of unit cells using the above value of α . Considering k_1 and k_2 corresponding to $N = 8$ and 16 respectively, the value of k_3 ($N=32$) can be calculated using eq. (3) (here N_i/N_{i+1} is always equal to 0.5).

Fig 5. Transverse shear stiffness predicted for large number of unit cells ($n \sim 4$ million) with $\alpha = 1.69$.

Thus using successive calculations the transverse shear stiffness for very large number of unit cells can be estimated. Figure 5 shows the stiffness predicted with $\alpha = 1.69$. For a very large number of unit cells, the transverse shear stiffness converged to $5.824 \times 10^5 N/m$.

4.3 Deflection Comparison: The FE model is analyzed under pressure load. One can note that the classical lamination theory which assumes infinitely large transverse shear stiffness makes the plate very stiff, and the deflections are significantly smaller than the deflections from the SDPT analysis (Fig. 6).

Fig 6. Deflection comparison between the FE 1D plate model and analytical model (CLPT and SDPT)

The error in the 1-D plate deflection without considering transverse shear is 80%. This demonstrates the effect of shear on the panel, that it is an important stiffness property that cannot be neglected. When the transverse shear stiffness term

A_{55} was included, the maximum 1D plate deflection is about 4% less than that of finite element analysis. The results show that the proposed homogenization procedure can be used to approximate the ITPS as a homogenous orthotropic plate for the purpose of calculating maximum deflection.

5. Summary

The homogenization of a corrugated core sandwich panel as a two dimensional (2-D) orthotropic plate was performed. A representative volume element of the panel was analyzed to obtain the equivalent stiffness properties through finite element based homogenization. A method is also proposed to estimate the transverse shear stiffness of the equivalent plate. The panel was analyzed under pressure load and the deflection was compared to that of an analytical model. The deflections of 1D plate with and without shear stiffness demonstrated the effect of transverse shear on the model.

Acknowledgements

This research is sponsored by NASA under a cooperative agreement (No. NNX08AB40A). Any opinions, findings, and conclusions or recommendations expressed in this material are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the National Aeronautics and Space Administration

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